

October 6th 1977

Dear Jean,

I hope these few lines will find you happy, successful and well!

I don't know if you are aware of my wish to play again with you on Scottsdale where I'll give my recital on April 23rd 1978 - your presence would be a great pleasure, remembering our meeting in Phoenix! Could you write to me directly if you can be my partner for this program:

- : Schubert Arpeggione
- : Brahms Op. 99

- : Debussy Lento
- : Beethoven Op. 69

I'll play in Phoenix 3 orchestral concerts just before this recital -

Could you tell me your fee? of course, I'll

Secure in addition your return Air
Fare from Austin -

with warmest wishes, dear Jean,
Yours very sincerely,

Pierre Fournier

Pierre Fournier

14 Chateau Banquet

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Switzerland

BY AIR MAIL
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Miss Jean Barr
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N.Y. 21 Nov.

Dear Jean.

A few lines only to tell you how pleased
I have been to play with such a wonderful
artist and to know such a wonderful person as
you & many thanks for your presence, your
beautiful piano playing - I do hope to see
you again as soon as possible -

Many warm wishes for a very happy
New Year - many regards to our friends
and accept, dear Jean, my personal
and affectionate thoughts.

Pierre Fournier